

Pest management and control INSECTS

Insectary evaluation of insecticides to control rice stink bugs

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Rice bugs (*Leptocorisa oratorius*) were reared by the method described by Valencia and Heinrichs (this issue). Rice variety IR36 plants at the flowering stage were used as test plants. Three tests were conducted.

In test 1, four panicles were sprayed. In tests 2 and 3, four hills were sprayed on a turntable. In tests 1 and 2, concentrations were based on manufacturers' recommendations. In test 3, new insecticides were compared with monocrotophos and were applied at the rate of 0.75

Table 1. Activity^a of insecticides applied as foliar sprays to control rice bugs. IRRI greenhouse, 1979.

Insecticide	Concentration (%)	Mortality (%)
<i>Test 1</i>		
<i>Effective</i>		
Monocrotophos 16.8 EC	0.05	100 a
Endosulfan 35 EC	0.06	100 a
Chlorpyrifos 40 EC	0.016	100a
Phosphamidon 50 EC	0.07	100 a
Acephate 40 EC	0.09	99 a
Triazophos 40 EC	0.07	98 a
Carbaryl 85 WP	0.12	91 b
<i>Intermediate</i>		
MIPC 50 WP	0.07	74 bc
Carbophenothion 40 EC	0.09	73 bc
Methyl parathion 50 EC	0.07	56 c
Chlorpyrifos + BPMC 31.6 EC	0.14	50 c
<i>Ineffective</i>		
Carbofuran 12 F	0.01	19 d
Azinphos ethy 140 EC	0.07	3 e
MTMC 30 EC	0.11	3e
Control		3e
<i>Test 2</i>		
<i>Effective</i>		
Monocrotophos + mevinphos 20.2 EC	0.06	100 a
Diazinon 20 EC	0.21	100a

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Table 1 cont'd.

Insecticide	Concentration (%)	Mortality ^a (%)
Fenitrothion 30 EC	0.05	98 ab
Pirimiphos methyl 25 EC	0.03	85 b
<i>Ineffective</i>		
FMC 35001 20 EC	0.02	28 c
BPMC 50 EC	0.05	23 c
Ethion 40 EC	0.04	8 cd
Permethrin 10 EC	0.01	0 d
Control		0 d

^a Insects were placed on treated panicles 1 day after treatment and mortality recorded 48 hours after infestation. Means followed by a common letter are not significantly different at 5% level. Effective =>80% mortality, intermediate = 50-79% mortality, ineffective = <50% mortality.

Table 2. Knockdown and residual effect of insecticides against rice bugs. IRRI greenhouse, 1979.

Insecticide	Mortality (%)		
	1 DAT	7 DAT	14 DAT
UC54229 100 Tech.	100.0 a	100.0 a	56.7 b
M 9918 20 OE	100.0 a	96.7 ab	76.7 a
M 10604 20 OE	100.0 a	86.7 b	43.3 bc
Monocrotophos 16.8 EC	100.0 a	36.1 c	20.0 c
Methiocarb 50 WP	100.0 a	20.0 cd	3.3 d
Methidathion 40 EC	93.3 a	10.0 de	0.0 d
UC 27867 50 WP	83.3 a	0.0 e	3.3 d
Cypermethrin 5 EC	56.7 b	3.3 e	0.0 d
Dioxacarb 50 WP	10.0 c	0.0 e	0.0 d
Dioxathion 96 EC	3.3 c	3.3 e	0.0 d
UC SF-1 40 F	3.3 c	3.3 e	0.0 d
RP 32861 20 EC	0.0 c	13.3 de	0.0 d
EXP 5494 25 EC	0.0 c	3.3 e	0.0 d
RH 0308 48 EC	0.0 c	0.0 e	3.3 d
RH 0994 48 EC	0.0 c	3.3 e	3.3 d
Control	0.0 c	3.3 e	0.0 d

^a In a column, means followed by a common letter are not significantly different at the 5% level. DAT= days after treatment.

Mass rearing of rice stink bugs

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Rice bugs, *Leptocorisa* spp., occur throughout Asia. Heavy feeding on rice grains in the milky stage prevents grain development and results in unfilled

kg a.i./ha, based on 160,000 hills and 1,000 liters of spray solution per hectare.

One day after spraying, panicles were placed in a mylar film cage with 10 two-day-old female rice bug adults. Mortality was recorded 48 hours later. In test 3, residual activity was measured by determining mortality 7 and 14 days after treatment (DAT). Treatments were replicated four times.

Seven insecticides in test 1 and four in test 2 were effective ($\geq 80\%$ mortality) at the concentrations tested (Table 1). In test 3 (Table 2), UC 54229, M 9918, M 10604, methiocarb, methidathion, and UC 27867 were effective 1 DAT. M 9918 had the longest residual activity, causing 77% mortality 14 DAT. ■

grains. The primary control is spraying or dusting with insecticides. Little evaluation of insecticides for control has been published, primarily because of the difficulty of conducting field tests. We have developed a mass rearing technique for *L. oratorius* which supplies sufficient insects to evaluate insecticides in the insectary and laboratory. The method